

Autism vaccine injury claim denied due to science missteps

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The Vaccine Injury Compensation Program (VICP) case (1) has multiple science related mistakes on both sides which led to the wrong ruling.

The case says: “molecular mimicry theory of causation, based on the similarity between a protein in the pertussis portion of the DTaP vaccination and one in the folate receptor”.

The molecular mimicry theory is unnecessary. The DTaP vaccine contains residual cow’s milk proteins (2), one of which is the folate receptor alpha (FRA) protein. Therefore the vaccine can cause the development of folate receptor alpha antibodies (FRAA). Casamino acids and casein derived from cow’s milk are used as growth media for vaccine manufacture and the final vaccine contains residual milk proteins from the manufacturing process.

AAAAI: Kids May React to Milk Proteins in DPT Shot
<https://www.medpagetoday.org/meetingcoverage/aaaai/25520?vpass=1>

As we have explained in great detail (3–5), the first step is vaccine-induced IgE antibody mediated sensitization (development of allergy) to FRA. We know that the child was exhibiting milk allergy symptoms and therefore had IgE mediated sensitization to one or more milk proteins. The allergy was not severe enough and we know the child was able to consume milk. Once sensitization occurs, subsequent milk consumption leads to the synthesis of IgG4 antibodies to those same proteins such as FRA and other milk proteins. This is very well understood from allergy research (6–9). Ramaekers et al. (10) have shown that FRA IgG4 antibodies play the biggest role in blocking/binding human folate receptors thus resulting in cerebral folate deficiency and autism.

It should be noted that each subsequent milk protein containing vaccine acts as a milk allergy and anti-milk protein IgE antibody booster shot (11).

This establishes the DTaP vaccine’s role in creating the anti-folate receptor antibodies. It is important to understand that consuming milk results in IgG4 synthesis against FRA **only** because of prior sensitization by the milk containing vaccine. Milk in the diet alone in a healthy person will **not** result in IgG4 synthesis against FRA. In other words, dietary milk alone cannot cause these autoantibodies. Sensitization to the milk protein by a vaccine is absolutely required before dietary milk can begin to generate autoantibodies.

As Ramaekers et al. (10) describe, the IgG4 levels will depend on milk consumption. Due to milk allergy symptoms, the child’s milk intake varied. At some point milk was stopped but other dairy products were still included. So this establishes that FRA IgG4 levels and CSF 5MTHF (cerebrospinal fluid 5-methyltetrahydrofolate) levels varied during this period depending on milk exposure in the diet. Milk was consumed from 2006 (shortly after 18 months old) to July 2007.

The CSF 5MTHF was only measured once in 2011. The variation in CSF 5MTHF due to milk consumption and the resulting transient cerebral folate deficiency can result in permanent damage because the brain is growing and a crucial nutrient is in short supply. No conclusions about transient cerebral folate deficiency during 18 month to ~2 years of age can be drawn using measurements performed much later in 2011. The 5MTHF reference levels indicate what is considered normal at any given time. However, the effect of sustained “low normal” or transient below normal levels cannot be ascertained from a single measurement at a point in time 4 years after the damage occurred.

While the effect of FRAA on CSF 5MTHF levels has been the focus, it must be understood that the FRAA are blocking folate to numerous other organs as well. This systemic impact may mean that the 40-128 nmol/L reference range of CSF 5MTHF applicable to a normal healthy person may not be applicable to an FRAA positive individual. In other words, higher CSF 5MTHF may be needed to make up for sub optimal bodily functions resulting from FRAA blocking folate uptake to other organs and tissues such as thyroid, salivary, bronchial glands, alveolar lining etc. (12).

The science was not correctly described by either side. The decision to deny the petition is therefore wrong due to the details described above. Milk protein containing vaccines such as (DTaP/Prevnar 13/ActHib) do indeed result in the development of FRA mediated autism.

Here is a description of the process by which milk protein containing vaccines cause the development of autism that may be appropriate for lay persons.

<https://www.quora.com/Is-there-any-scientific-proof-that-vaccines-cause-autism/answers/84615265>

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